

1A: COA Development Tool for Julia

Condition	Narrative Description	Stimulus Classes	Potentially Aversive Stimuli Included?	Materials and Implementers
A	Julia does not have access to attention or tangible items. She is not expected to work.	N/A		
B	Julia is required to complete academic demands alone.		Yes	Academic work
C	Julia is required to complete academic demands but has her teacher assisting with her work.	Attention	Yes	Academic work
D	Julia has free access to preferred tangible items and activities with no attention.	Tangible		High-preferred tangibles
E	Julia has free access to preferred tangible items and activities with attention from her teacher.	Tangible, Attention		High-preferred tangibles Teacher
F	Julia has free access to attention from a preferred teacher.	Attention		Teacher
G	Julia has free access to tangible items but ones that are not as highly preferred.	Tangible		Low-preferred tangibles